

INFORMATION AND ANALYTICAL SUPPORT FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF A HIGHER EDUCATION ORGANIZATION

M.Y. Khakimova

Free applicant TDPU

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Abstract. *In the modern world, the quality of training specialists in universities is becoming a key factor in their successful professional activity. The article focuses on the need to adapt curricula to the requirements of modern educational and professional standards. This requires active cooperation of all university departments, which includes coordination between faculties and departments. This is the only way to create a unified system for training highly qualified personnel who will meet the current requirements of the labor market and will be able to successfully compete in the international arena. Involving employers in the training process and introducing practice-oriented programs will help provide graduates with the necessary skills and competencies.*

Keywords: *education, management, didactic support, higher education institution, teacher, management coordination.*

Introduction. In modern society, in the field of education, the activity of the information and analytical support system is aimed at solving the following problems:

- design and implementation of the educational process at the macro level of the education system; creation of conditions for the implementation of activities and development of educational organizations;
- assistance to educational organizations in the process of mastering and implementing federal state educational standards of various levels of education, implementing targeted federal, regional and municipal programs of training, education, development, youth policy, etc.;
- motivation of management and teaching staff of educational organizations for professional and personal self-development; scientific, educational, methodological and information support for all participants in the educational process [2].

Methodology. The solution of these problems is ensured by the implementation of the following functions by the IAO system:

Functions of the information and analytical support system in the field of education

1. The implementation of the information function involves the creation of a database that includes regulatory, scientific, methodological, pedagogical and other information, as well as factual information about the objects of management.

The use of the database simplifies the process of informing employees of the educational organization about new directions in education and innovations in the field of psychological, pedagogical, methodological science, methodological and regulatory framework for organizing the educational process, modern educational technologies, programs and educational and methodological complexes.

The implementation of this function is also aimed at creating conditions for the exchange and transfer of experience both within the team of employees and between teachers of various educational organizations: a bank of educational and methodological materials, an information and library system, etc. An important role in this process is given to the intra-organizational information distribution system, as well as the delimitation of access rights to information sources for all employees of the educational organization.

2. The organization and monitoring of the professional and information needs of managers, teachers and other employees of educational organizations is carried out in the process of implementing the analytical function of the IAO system.

During monitoring, data on the status and results of methodological work in educational organizations is collected and analyzed in order to determine areas for improving the educational process and the activities of the teaching staff. Also, a mandatory and necessary requirement for monitoring is the identification of objective, subjective and scholastic difficulties that arise in the educational process and have a didactic and methodological nature. Identification of these difficulties acts as a criterion condition for analytical work implemented by the IAO system in the field of education. The most important aspect of analytical work is control and accounting operations with factual data, numerical parameters and quantitative indicators characterizing the educational and training processes in the organization.

In general, the implementation of the analytical function of the IAO system in the field of education is aimed at increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of the process of studying, generalizing and disseminating advanced pedagogical experience.

3. The most comprehensive function in the IAO system is the organizational and methodological one. The implementation of this function involves identifying and analyzing the requests of teachers and other employees of educational organizations within the framework of the educational process: methodological support, support and provision of practical assistance, both in pedagogical activity and in preparation for certification in inter-certification periods. As a result,

the work of the system should be aimed at implementing the processes of forecasting, planning and organizing advanced training and professional retraining of the management and teaching staff of the organization, as well as providing information and methodological assistance in the process of continuous education.

To solve these problems, the information and analytical system creates, maintains and constantly updates the list of heads, teachers and other employees of educational organizations sent for advanced training, certification, special training and retraining; a database of the main areas of implementation of the educational process, various factors, as well as educational programs that ensure this implementation.

Important aspects of the manifestation of the organizational and methodological function of the IAO system in an educational organization are information and methodological support for the preparation and certification of students; defining a set of issues of methodological and information support for specialized training in general education organizations, as well as ensuring the acquisition of library funds with educational, methodological, scientific and other literature, coordination of methodological activities in an educational organization with the relevant divisions of education management bodies and organizations of additional professional pedagogical education.

4. Popularization and explanation of the results of the latest pedagogical research for the heads and teaching staff of educational organizations occurs in the process of performing the consulting function of the IAO system. This requires comprehensive consulting work with all participants in the educational process and employees of the structural divisions of the educational system.

The IAO system of any educational organization is integrated into the structure of information and analytical systems of a higher level in the educational environment, according to the administrative hierarchy of educational organizations on the scale of districts, cities, regions and the country as a whole.

The structuring and functioning of information and analytical support systems in educational organizations must comply with the requirements of qualified scientific systematization [1].

The functioning of IAO systems in the field of education can be carried out in various directions. A.K. Nesterov in his research highlights the following as such directions:

- updating and continuous development of pedagogical information and methodological resources;
- optimization of managerial activities of specialists in the process of solving management problems and forecasting the development of educational organizations; design of pedagogical information technologies for training;
- maximum implementation of the capabilities of IAO systems for the professionalization of the process of training students in the field of information technology proficiency.

The author considers the reorientation from advanced versions of database management systems to a qualitatively different level, which allows for expert analytical actions; data interpretation; condition diagnostics; monitoring; forecasting; planning and training, as the main criterion parameters for the functioning of information and analytical systems [5].

IAO systems are not homogeneous, but have some objective features determined by the internal structure of the system itself and the principles of its construction. The following characteristics act as objective distinctive features of a particular IAO system:

- stability of IAO systems to the action of various external interferences
- due to the absence of subjective prejudices; the information-analytical system does not make hasty conclusions, therefore the capabilities of the system user in the process of making a particular decision are significantly expanded; IAO systems do not issue the first found, but the optimal solution in accordance with the criteria conditions; the information array of data in the information-analytical system can be very large, objectively exceeding such volumes of database management systems.

Conclusion. It should be noted that any IAO system has real possibilities of its application and with its help not all existing problems of educational organization management can be solved.

Nevertheless, the correct use of IAO systems and corresponding technologies in many cases remains the only real way to prepare and make informed management decisions [1].

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